

Synthesis of some new azetidin-2-ones as potential antimicrobial agents

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Abstract : Some new 2-hydroxy-5-(phenyl azo)-3-chloro-*N*-phenyl azetidin-2-one (**4**) and 2'-hydroxy-5'-(phenyl azo)-*N*-(1'',3''-diketo phenyl amine)-3-chloro azetidin-2-ones (**5**) have been synthesised and their structures have been established on the basis of spectroscopic data. Compounds **4(o,r)** and **5(o,r)** showed significant antimicrobial activity. Compound **4(o)** is most active against *S. typhi*, *A. niger* and *C. albicans* as compared to control drug chloramphenicol and fluconazole.

Keywords : Azetidin-2-ones, microbial agent.

The importance and structural diversity of biologically active β -lactam antibiotics has led to the development of efficient approaches for the construction of substituted azetidin-2-ones¹. The phenomenal success of penicillin and related antibiotics² as magic bullets has found an extensive β -lactam research in many industrial and academic laboratories. The various families of β -lactam antibiotics differ in their spectrum of antibacterial activity and susceptibility of β -lactamase³. The emergence of many antibiotic resistant strains of once sensitive bacteria is a major theme of current research and this fact has triggered a renewed interest in the building of new β -lactams from two precursors viz. imines and diketoamino analogs. Some of the synthesised azetidin-2-ones have been evaluated *in vitro* antimicrobial susceptibility test against different microbes.

Results and discussion

Condensation of substituted azo-salicylaldehydes (**1**) with substituted anilines in ethyl alcohol furnished imine (**2**) and with substituted hydrazides in EtOH yielded 1,3-diketoamino analogs (**3**). The β -lactam moiety in compound **2** and **3** was introduced by cycloaddition of chloroacetyl chloride in the presence of triethylamine in dry dioxane, that afforded 2-hydroxy-5-(phenylazo)-3-chloro-*N*-phenyl azetidin-2-one, **4(a-r)** and 2'-hydroxy-5'-(phenyl azo)-*N*-(1'',3''-diketoamino)-3-chloroazetidin-2-ones, **5(a-r)** (Scheme 1). Purity of the compounds was monitored by TLC.

Synthesis of β -lactams through this route involves the initial nucleophilic attack of the enolate ion on the azomethine carbon followed by cyclisation.

Scheme 1

Antimicrobial screening : Compounds **4** and **5** (**a, d, h, k, o** and **r**) were screened *in vitro* for their antimicrobial susceptibility against five bacterial pathogens namely *B. anthracis*, *S. aureus*, *E. coli*, *S. typhi*, *P. aeruginosa* and five fungal microbes namely *A. niger*, *A. flavus*, *A. fumigatus*, *C. albicans* and *C. neoformans* at 15.62 to 4000 $\mu\text{g/ml}$ using

Note

serial dilution tube technique. Antibacterial zone of inhibition of same compounds were determined using Kirby Bauer susceptibility disk technique⁴. A systematic perusal of the data showed that with the increase in concentration of the compounds, the decrease in turbidity takes place in tube dilutions while the zone of inhibition increases in petridishes. The greatest antibacterial activity is associated with R = -Cl(*p*), R' = -Cl(*p*) **4** and **5(o)** and R = -Cl(*m*), R' = -NO₂(*m*) **4** and **5(k)**. Compound **5(a)** R = -Cl(*o*), R' = -Cl(*o*) showed significant antifungal activity. The antibacterial activity follows the pattern : *S. aureus* > *B. anthraxis* > *E. coli* > *S. typhi* > *P. aeruginosa*.

Following observations were made on the basis of antimicrobial screening :

(a) Chloro substituent at *para* position and nitro moiety at *meta* position are most favourable for activity.

(b) The least MIC for *S. typhi* is probably due to non-secretion of β-lactamase from this bacterium.

(c) Replacement of chloro group from *para* position and nitro group from *meta* position reduces the antibacterial activity.

Table 1. Physical data of azetidin-2-ones (**4**)

Compd.	R	R'	Yield (%)	M.p. (°C)	Molecular formula	Found/ (Calcd.)%N
4a	Cl(<i>o</i>)	Cl(<i>o</i>)	38	178	C ₂₁ H ₁₄ N ₃ O ₂ Cl ₃	9.30 (9.40)
b	Cl(<i>o</i>)	Cl(<i>m</i>)	41	150	C ₂₁ H ₁₄ N ₃ O ₂ Cl ₃	9.28 (9.40)
c	Cl(<i>o</i>)	Cl(<i>p</i>)	57	180	C ₂₁ H ₁₄ N ₃ O ₂ Cl ₃	9.31 (9.40)
d	Cl(<i>o</i>)	NO ₂ (<i>o</i>)	35	123	C ₂₁ H ₁₄ N ₄ O ₄ Cl ₂	12.20 (12.25)
e	Cl(<i>o</i>)	NO ₂ (<i>m</i>)	43	138	C ₂₁ H ₁₄ N ₄ O ₄ Cl ₂	12.18 (12.20)
f	Cl(<i>o</i>)	NO ₂ (<i>p</i>)	53	152	C ₂₁ H ₁₄ N ₄ O ₄ Cl ₂	12.21 (12.25)
g	Cl(<i>m</i>)	Cl(<i>o</i>)	49	135	C ₂₁ H ₁₄ N ₃ O ₂ Cl ₃	9.29 (9.40)
h	Cl(<i>m</i>)	Cl(<i>m</i>)	52	128	C ₂₁ H ₁₄ N ₃ O ₂ Cl ₃	9.33 (9.40)
i	Cl(<i>m</i>)	Cl(<i>p</i>)	59	138	C ₂₁ H ₁₄ N ₃ O ₂ Cl ₃	9.30 (9.40)
j	Cl(<i>m</i>)	NO ₂ (<i>o</i>)	37	160	C ₂₁ H ₁₄ N ₄ O ₄ Cl ₂	12.20 (12.25)
k	Cl(<i>m</i>)	NO ₂ (<i>m</i>)	46	165	C ₂₁ H ₁₄ N ₄ O ₄ Cl ₂	12.23 (12.20)
l	Cl(<i>m</i>)	NO ₂ (<i>p</i>)	50	145	C ₂₁ H ₁₄ N ₄ O ₄ Cl ₂	12.19 (12.25)
m	Cl(<i>p</i>)	Cl(<i>o</i>)	56	133	C ₂₁ H ₁₄ N ₃ O ₂ Cl ₃	9.24 (9.40)
n	Cl(<i>p</i>)	Cl(<i>m</i>)	58	143	C ₂₁ H ₁₄ N ₃ O ₂ Cl ₃	9.32 (9.40)
o	Cl(<i>p</i>)	Cl(<i>p</i>)	63	187	C ₂₁ H ₁₄ N ₃ O ₂ Cl ₃	9.31 (9.40)
p	Cl(<i>p</i>)	NO ₂ (<i>o</i>)	60	155	C ₂₁ H ₁₄ N ₄ O ₄ Cl ₂	12.18 (12.25)
q	Cl(<i>p</i>)	NO ₂ (<i>m</i>)	65	159	C ₂₁ H ₁₄ N ₄ O ₄ Cl ₂	12.22 (12.20)
r	Cl(<i>p</i>)	NO ₂ (<i>p</i>)	62	172	C ₂₁ H ₁₄ N ₄ O ₄ Cl ₂	12.20 (12.25)

Table 2. Physical data of azetidin-2-ones (**5**)

Compd	R	R'	Yield (%)	M.p. (°C)	Molecular formula	Found/ (Calcd.)%N
5a	Cl(<i>o</i>)	Cl(<i>o</i>)	33	140	C ₂₄ H ₁₈ N ₅ O ₄ Cl ₃	12.50 (12.80)
b	Cl(<i>o</i>)	Cl(<i>m</i>)	40	152	C ₂₄ H ₁₈ N ₅ O ₄ Cl ₃	12.62 (12.80)
c	Cl(<i>o</i>)	Cl(<i>p</i>)	39	125	C ₂₄ H ₁₈ N ₅ O ₄ Cl ₃	12.60 (12.80)
d	Cl(<i>o</i>)	NO ₂ (<i>o</i>)	42	180	C ₂₄ H ₁₈ N ₆ O ₆ Cl ₂	15.01 (15.08)
e	Cl(<i>o</i>)	NO ₂ (<i>m</i>)	47	143	C ₂₄ H ₁₈ N ₆ O ₆ Cl ₂	15.03 (15.08)
f	Cl(<i>o</i>)	NO ₂ (<i>p</i>)	52	192	C ₂₄ H ₁₈ N ₅ O ₄ Cl ₃	15.00 (15.08)
g	Cl(<i>m</i>)	Cl(<i>o</i>)	43	153	C ₂₄ H ₁₈ N ₅ O ₄ Cl ₃	12.72 (12.80)
h	Cl(<i>m</i>)	Cl(<i>m</i>)	37	138	C ₂₄ H ₁₈ N ₅ O ₄ Cl ₃	12.60 (12.80)
i	Cl(<i>m</i>)	Cl(<i>p</i>)	59	129	C ₂₄ H ₁₈ N ₅ O ₄ Cl ₃	12.63 (12.80)
j	Cl(<i>m</i>)	NO ₂ (<i>o</i>)	52	172	C ₂₄ H ₁₈ N ₆ O ₆ Cl ₂	15.02 (15.08)
k	Cl(<i>m</i>)	NO ₂ (<i>m</i>)	63	178	C ₂₄ H ₁₈ N ₆ O ₆ Cl ₂	15.00 (15.08)
l	Cl(<i>m</i>)	NO ₂ (<i>p</i>)	65	182	C ₂₄ H ₁₈ N ₆ O ₆ Cl ₂	15.04 (15.08)
m	Cl(<i>p</i>)	Cl(<i>o</i>)	44	122	C ₂₄ H ₁₈ N ₅ O ₄ Cl ₃	12.50 (12.80)
n	Cl(<i>p</i>)	Cl(<i>m</i>)	57	118	C ₂₄ H ₁₈ N ₅ O ₄ Cl ₃	12.61 (12.80)
o	Cl(<i>p</i>)	Cl(<i>p</i>)	60	135	C ₂₄ H ₁₈ N ₅ O ₄ Cl ₃	12.68 (12.80)
p	Cl(<i>p</i>)	NO ₂ (<i>o</i>)	54	168	C ₂₄ H ₁₈ N ₆ O ₆ Cl ₂	15.02 (15.08)
q	Cl(<i>p</i>)	NO ₂ (<i>m</i>)	59	164	C ₂₄ H ₁₈ N ₆ O ₆ Cl ₂	15.01 (15.08)
r	Cl(<i>p</i>)	NO ₂ (<i>p</i>)	62	185	C ₂₄ H ₁₈ N ₆ O ₆ Cl ₂	15.04 (15.08)

Experimental

All melting points were taken in open capillaries and are uncorrected. IR spectra were scanned on Perkin-Elmer-337 Infracord Spectrometer and ¹H NMR spectra on a Varian EM-390 MHz instrument.

2-Hydroxy-5-(p-chlorophenylazo)-chloro-N-(p-chlorophenyl)azetidin-2-one, 4(o) : Compound **2** (0.001 M) was added to a constantly stirred mixture of 1,4-dioxane (20 ml), triethylamine (0.16 ml, 0.001 M) and chloroacetylchloride (0.09 ml, 0.001 M) at 0–5 °C. The reaction mixture was then stirred for 8 h. The filtrate was concentrated under reduced pressure and poured into ice-cold water. The product so obtained was recrystallised from methanol as light brown crystals, yield 35%; m.p. 145 °C; IR (KBr) 3512 (O-H str.), 1760 (C=O str., β-lactam ring), 1578 cm⁻¹ (N=N str.); ¹H NMR (DMSO-*d*₆) δ 4.12 (1H, s, OH), 3.21 (1H, d, CH-N), 2.43 (1H, d, CH-Cl), 7.1–7.6 (11H, m, ArH).

2'-Hydroxy-5'-(p-chlorophenylazo)-N-(1'',3''-diketo-p-chloroamine)-3-chloro azetidin-2-one, 5(o) : A procedure similar to that for **4(o)** was followed. Yield 60%, m.p. 132 °C; IR (KBr) 3473 (O-H str.), 3075 (N-H str.), 1589 (N=N str.), 1635 (C=O, 1,3-diketo), 1762 cm⁻¹ (C=O, β-lactam ring); ¹H NMR (DMSO-*d*₆) δ 10.03 (1H, s, NH^a), 8.0 (1H,

s, NH^b), 3.93 (1H, s, OH), 3.42 (2H, s, CH₂), 2.9 (1H, d, CH^c-N), 2.36 (1H, d, CH^d-Cl), 7.3–7.7 (11H, m, ArH).

Similarly other compounds (**4a-r** and **5a-r**) were prepared (Tables 1 and 2) and their structures were elucidated by IR and NMR spectra.

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References

1. B. Alcaide, P. Almendros and N. M. Alonso, *J. Org. Chem.*, 2004, **69**, 993.
2. P. Campomanes, M. I. Menedez and T. L. Sordo, *J. Org. Chem.*, 2003, **68**, 6685; G. Cremonesi, P. D. Croce and C. L. Rosa, *Tetrahedron*, 2004, **60**, 93; J. M. Parmar, J. J. Modha and A. R. Parikh, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. B*, 1999, **38**, 440; P. Sharma, A. Kumar and S. Sharma, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. B*, 2004, **43**, 385.
3. A. David Evans and J. Michael William, *Tetrahedron*, 1988, **40**, 5065; S. D. Srivastava and N. Guru, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 2000, **77**, 400; Y. Dejaegher and N. De. Kimpe, *J. Org. Chem.*, 2004, **69**, 5974; S. B. More and R. N. Chavan, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 2002, **79**, 768.
4. A. William David and L. Thomas, "Leouke, Foye's Principle of Medicinal Chemistry", 5th ed., 2002, 821.